

Behaviour traits of a narcissistic psychopath (initial draft, part 2)

Approach

A university program was created close to the place of her residence with focus on computer science. Different dynamics started to circulate among the subjects of interest and people involved in the creation of a new institute. As far back as 2007, interest groups started to approach the victim, knowing on what possibilities can be obtained as a subject who graduated in the US holding a US social security number. As per state politics, some individual was chosen to be the primary contact of the victim to conduct a school project, not as faculty member, but as a system administrator. In some unforeseen cases, wrong people get granted access to data infrastructures and communication control of territorial institutes. Such individuals, upon graduation obtained employment in a technological organization, where instead of focusing and finishing his studies, was being outsourced as an individual from the crime syndicate to the US and other places. At this point, one needs to understand the distinction between a direct employee of the company or research institute or a person being outsourced. Principal motives are not always the same as well as the selection committee of who and why somebody arrives at the specific post is not necessarily determined by the coherent group of people. Because of the shown luxury of employers that manage high money turnover, one loses motivation to finish the studies or write a thesis, as such work requires effort, persistence, creativity and discipline. Also, not to every individual, structural and argumentative writing presents an easy challenge to complete or persistence that quality work will emerge of the given project initiative. In this particular member state in question, a library system registers each academic work in a digitalised way, a big portion of academic work was not ever even written by the person who holds the degree, but some educated, structural or intelligent individual that cannot find employment because, in some cases, is unfit to conduct immoral things at the workplace.

Within the realm of IT related work disciplines, the hierarchy of acceptance and decisions on who will be allowed to partake in the development process is a matter of personal preferences for the most time. In this particular member state, one can obtain employment only on nepotism and who-you-know bases. Even the types of interviews take upon a very different form of evaluating a suitable candidate. The mentality is, the characteristics shall be fit to conduct work in realm of team spirit, quality assurance of the individual's skillset is another topic of interest.

Some individuals, having access to administrative settings of a system, use their skills not to teach a coworker to become better acquainted with the skillset, but to study and observe the individual to victimize them as per being dependent on their services and manipulate their behaviour. Malicious interests of such individuals, show in grandiosity and behavioural challenges as they think they can rule the world by victimizing their preys. High degree of vengeance and maliciousness, seeking revenge and incapacitating their victims in a most brutal way. A high degree of unprofessionalism lies at the core of such individuals that think they are better than anyone else and can use some computer skillset to manipulate victims. For example, such individuals use system settings in the backend to manipulate the user's frontend in such a way, that the user, ignorant of the manipulation techniques done in the backend, needs to call for assistance because the front end is not working as it should.

Computers in general are stupid entities and behave only on sequential commands, normally done either by accident or purposefully to cause direct harm and manipulate the victim to obtain something of their interest.

Once the victim was targeted by the crime syndicate and has sustained some sort of unethical damage done by one of the members of the organization, that person can no longer escape the organization because it is being leveraged to either keep quiet or to conduct unethical things for the sake of defending the criminal ring in operation.

Study of an individual

Targeted individuals of a crime syndicate interest group, get studied in details of all their behaviour motives and aspirations. Once put in a so-called golden cage by the malicious interest group, the victim slowly gets incapacitated by digital means (take over of communication channels - e-mail, phone number, post) to be forced into cooperation. As a very old school method, the easiest way to incapacitate someone from having any credibility is to use sanitariat data manipulation techniques, especially the one with abusing the mental health labels found in the Statistical manual of psychiatric diseases. As the western system completely revolves around the one dimensional abuse of psychiatric opinions that can either make or destroy an individual based on some sort of territorial control and financial motives, no human dignity, wishes or values get respected by the narcissistic psychopath whos motive to drive their productivity is to cause purposeful harm to the chosen victim.

Once the victim is studied and the crime syndicate knows of their motives to be alive, to obtain the control of territory, they use the most unethical methods to physically and mentally incapacitate a victim in a state where once labeled with a mental disease, the victim has absolutely no say in the explanation of unethical acts done by the crime syndicate to erase traits of their behaviour and motives.

A clear rejection by the victim

Each individual has the right to say a clear No to insinuations and provocations done by such individuals that due to some neglect and lack of affirmation from past decisions, take a victim and abuse their creativity to the extent to make her a disabled person. Each human decision and life shall be governed by the fundamental codex of human rights and a free choice. A person has the right to say no to unethical treatment, the person has the right to not sustain torture, the person has the right to choose to be connected with who he or she wants. Such are the theoretical facts, but when a victim is victimized by a narcissistic psychopath, whose only motive to be alive and a source of motivation is to harm the victim, then with the victim having the label of mental illness, such individual protected by the crime syndicate, has absolutely no limits in abusing ethical or unethical means to cause harm and degrade his victim.

Imagining a state of mind of a narcissistic psychopath to commit such acts and violate all ethics and morals to obtain what does not belong to them, when in reality, such individual to the outside world shows the positivism and eagerness of a state of mind of their victim is the most horrific truth that the victim must live with for the rest of her life.

Gaslighting and complete digital control

Each step made by the victim is completely controlled by the crime syndicate. Each phone conversation is listened to, each set meeting by the phone interferes with corruption costs, each e-mail is read or not even delivered to the final destination, etc. The member state, which holds the person as a victim of their wrongdoings for spying purposes and money laundering and to put unauthorised people from the crime syndicate to positions where such individuals only cause harm or abuse information to allow unauthorised profit for their interest groups, with zero respect for human dignity and joy of creation of their victims.

The narcissistic psychopath went as far as forcing a medical doctor to write wrongful medical records of facts that were not true. It was unfortunate, that for the criminal to defend himself and not go to prison, an innocent sport club of table tennis was used to teach the kids to lie and not tell the truth. The victim, who has table tennis in her head and plays and understands it at a much higher level, was wrongfully accused of causing violence and put in a mental institute for breaching her human rights. In this time of her unjust and wrongful detention, the crime syndicate was deleting traces at the tribunal in a foreign country to allow a criminal or a narcissistic psychopath to freely walk the streets today. In such cases, when no human dignity, talents, human rights, protection of intellectual property are being taken into consideration, one must ask her or his self of what kind of individuals we want to design the world and the AI system, people that teach kids to lie, manipulate, cause purposeful harm, protect invasion of privacy and defend criminal acts because of some unjust and stupid political decisions?

Fair competition in a sports club

Question: is a win done by manipulation and fraud a win worth celebrating?

Re-evaluating the verification methods of innocence, of whether or not somebody is telling the truth regarding involvement of cooperation or theft, making a person disappear based on corruption and forging medical records while implicating a fraudulent story done by the state for political reasons, is all but a pleasant experience for the victim of the criminal.

Since the victim was studied profoundly by the crime syndicate, the obtained skillset of the victim was so broad, that the crime syndicate went as far as removing the transparency of table tennis competitions within the member state. Each positive thing that the victim wants to do, the crime syndicate is one step ahead with forging records. Unfortunately, for such instances, there shall be an institution that can oversee crimes committed in different member states and not rely solely on police accounts, when the overseeing party is unaware of the legal and other mechanics of take over of critical state infrastructure by members outside of the union.

Highest degree of abuse

The worst and the most worrisome act done by the crime syndicate was to conduct an interstate criminal investigation, just to in the end, put on stand an impersonated person that lied in court and set the criminal free to find another victim to abuse and destroy.

In the case study in question, this specific individual was kept hostage against her will in a state with poor legislations, allowing unfit political decisions to keep the system as is in control by specific interest groups. Throughout the exploration of facts, one worrisome instance came to life, not only to answer the question of who will be designing the next AI systems, but also:

Who is in charge of fundamental IT infrastructure in the member state within the European Union? Are EU citizens or somebody outside the EU that wants to control the EU through the open door allowed in one of such problematic member states?